

THE ROLE OF WISE WORDS IN THE WELL-BEING OF A CHILD

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10536060>

Abstract. *This article gives information about the role of wise words in the development of a child and how to promote communication and language development. Also, this article defines the role of school in the well-being of a child. Giving your children a few encouraging words each day will aid their mental growth and boost their moral strength. Positive phrases will make the kids feel better about them, and become more self-assured. Kids will develop self-confidence at their growing age, which is great.*

Keywords: *well-being, communication, language development, facial expression, success.*

РОЛЬ МУДРЫХ СЛОВ В БЛАГОПОЛУЧИИ РЕБЕНКА

Аннотация. *В этой статье дается информация о роли мудрых слов в развитии ребенка и о том, как способствовать общению и развитию речи. Также в этой статье определяется роль школы в благополучии ребенка. Дайте своим детям несколько ободряющих слов каждый день помогут их умственному развитию и укрепят моральную силу. Позитивные фразы заставят детей чувствовать себя лучше и станут более уверенными в себе. В зрелом возрасте у детей разовьется уверенность в себе, и это здорово.*

Ключевые слова: *благополучие, общение, развитие речи, мимика, успех.*

Giving your children a few encouraging words each day will aid their mental growth and boost their moral strength. Positive phrases will make the kids feel better about them, and become more self-assured. Kids will develop self-confidence at their growing age, which is great. It promotes communication and language development. It also supports social and emotional development. Even before your baby starts to talk, he/she communicates with you through facial expressions, body language and crying. It is important to respond to your child's signals.

Students' well-being and their success in and outside school depend on their ability to use their competences for democratic culture. Since well-being has many facets, improving students' well-being in schools requires a whole-school approach, involving both teachers and parents.

Schools should provide lessons focused on the responsible use of the Internet, the need to adopt a healthy lifestyle and how to prevent or cope with health problems, in collaboration with those involved, including health and social services, local authorities and civil society organisations and academic achievement and vice versa, i.e. well-being is a crucial prerequisite for achievement and achievement is essential for well-being. Physical activity is associated with improved learning and the ability to concentrate. Strong, supportive relationships provide students with the emotional resources to step out of their intellectual 'comfort zone' and explore new ideas and ways of thinking, which is fundamental to educational achievement.

Well-being is also important for developing important democratic competences. Positive emotions are associated with the development of flexibility and adaptability, openness to other

cultures and beliefs, self-efficacy and tolerance of ambiguity, all of which lie at the heart of the Council of Europe Reference Framework of Competences for Democratic Culture.

What are the challenges?

One of the challenges of trying to promote young people's well-being in school is the multi-faceted nature of well-being. There are a number of different types of well-being, all of which need to be promoted to some extent to create an overall sense of well-being in a person. So, it is not possible to improve students' well-being at school through single interventions or activities. Rather it requires the development of a 'culture' of well-being throughout the whole school and the active involvement of the whole staff, teaching and non-teaching, which can be difficult to achieve.

The promotion of well-being may sometimes appear to conflict with other school priorities, such as academic standards. Unreasonably high expectations, a regime of constant testing or an over-emphasis on the importance of academic performance may actually undermine student well-being.

In many cases schools do not have the freedom to make the changes to school life which might most benefit student well-being. They may have little control, for example, over formal examinations and tests, the content of curricula, the length of the school day or the physical school environment. Improving the physical environment of the school to make it more student-friendly, e.g. new furniture and fittings, carpeted areas, appropriate colour schemes, safe toilet areas, recreational areas; encouraging healthier eating by providing healthy options in the school canteen, e.g. avoiding high amounts of sugar, saturated fats and salt; working with parents to enhance students' achievement and sense of purpose in school, e.g. on healthy food, safe internet use and home-school communications.

Individual initiatives like these can be brought together at the whole-school level through a policy development process which 'mainstreams' well-being as a school issue. This means giving attention to the potential effects of new policies on individual well-being - of students, teachers and others. Addressing student well-being at school always goes hand in hand with action to protect the health and well-being of teachers and other staff at school.

Examples of folk oral creativity include the following resources: national customs, traditions, folk games, religious teachings, folk art, music, song, dance, etc. .Tales, one of the genres of folklore, introduce a child to happy feelings from an early age. The boy "travels" to faraway places together with the heroes of the fairy tale. They get to know life there. A fairy tale sharpens his mind, enriches his thinking, and develops his ability to imagine. The fluent, figurative language style of the story told in the family develops the child's speech. Bright, lifelike images have a deep impact on his emotions. He meets intelligent, kind-hearted, positive heroes, who grieve when disaster strikes, rejoice when they win, and punish evil and greedy people. The reliable moral ideas of the fairy tale told by adults in the family encourage the child to think, compare his behavior with the behavior of his favorite fairy tale characters, and in the image of the heroes, children learn to be fearless and truthful. Setting specific goals, working to achieve them, overcoming various obstacles, One of the main reasons why fairy tales, narratives, and other stories have a strong impact on a child's worldview is the legendary, understandable interpretation of reality in accordance with the child's age and worldview. Strong and fair people, cute animals close to the child's spiritual world appear as heroes of folklore. In the 13th-16th centuries, during

the reign of the Timurids, the children of nobles and courtiers were raised by healthy, intelligent, strong, polite, eloquent female nannies. Special attention is paid to the nanny's health, neatness and intelligence. The main task of nannies in raising a child was to feed him properly on time, dress him neatly, take him for a walk in the fresh air, teach him morals, and tell stories and epics. With the help of stories, fairy tales, narratives, war novels, nannies paid special attention to raising children with good morals, intelligence, promptness, and perseverance.

Proverbs are recognized as an important educational tool in the historical experience of the people. They are often used in everyday life. Especially the older members of the family use proverbs appropriately when encouraging children to be good, virtuous, satisfied, neat, and hardworking. A proverb is short and concise, figurative, grammatically and logically complete, a wise phrase, a sentence with a deep meaning, which encourages the child to think independently. It teaches you to express your thoughts clearly and concisely. It has a certain rhythmic form. Life experiences, attitude to society, history, mental state, ethical and aesthetic feelings, and positive qualities of ancestors are embodied in proverbs. Over the centuries, it has been refined among the people, and has become a concise and poetic form.

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